

Surgical Outcomes of Trigeminal Neuralgia and Medication Cost Benefit Analysis in the Preoperative and Postoperative Period

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Abstract:

Background: Trigeminal neuralgia (TGN) is a brief, paroxysmal intense pain syndrome which involves one or two branches of the fifth cranial nerve, triggered by cutaneous stimuli. Severity of TGN can be analysed by visual analogue scale scores (VAS) and disability adjusted life years (DALYs). The primary management of TGN is medical. Surgical management can be considered at failed medical management.

Objective: To compare the VAS scoring and DALY index after surgery in refractory TGN. Also, to estimate and compare the patient medical expenses in preoperative and postoperative period.

Methods: This was a prospective study conducted in a tertiary healthcare facility, Chennai, India with effect from January 2022 to March 2023. A total of ten patients were included. Patients with refractory (to medical management) idiopathic trigeminal neuralgia were enrolled and evaluated for disease severity based on VAS scores and economic burden was captured for pain management in the preoperative and postoperative period.

Results: The results showed that after six months follow up, in the postoperative period, the mean VAS scores had reduced from 6.5 to 2.5 in 7 out of 10 patients with medical management. Three patients had persistence of symptoms with VAS scores more than 5. Two patients developed pseudo meningocele in the immediate postoperative period. The average expenses per month in the preoperative period was Rupees 1200 and that in the postoperative period was Rupees 800. Two patients developed 7th nerve palsy and one patient developed sensory hearing loss of nearly 60 decibels in the operated side.

Conclusion: After surgery, the refractory TGN pain VAS scores had improved. Cost benefit analysis showed that postoperative expenses were economical. The surgical outcomes of the patients were good.

Keywords: Trigeminal neuralgia, Cost benefit analysis, Postoperative complications, Visual analogue scale, Disability adjusted life years.

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Introduction

Trigeminal neuralgia (TGN) can be classified as either primary (idiopathic) or secondary.[1] Primary TGN is more frequently observed in female patients between their 30s and 50s, with an annual incidence rate of 5.7 per 100,000 women and 2.5 per 100,000 men.[2] The peak incidence occurs in individuals aged 50 to 60 and increases with age. TGN is characterized by brief, intense, paroxysmal pain involving one or two branches of the fifth cranial nerve, often triggered by cutaneous stimuli. The diagnosis of typical TGN relies on five criteria: (a) paroxysmal sharp and shooting pain with periods of exacerbation and remission, (b)

pain following the distribution of the fifth cranial nerve, (c) a normal neurological examination with no significant loss of facial sensation, (d) magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) showing no mass lesions or demyelinating plaques, and (e) pain induced by cutaneous stimulation. [3-5] The trigeminal nerve (CN V) is the largest and most complex cranial nerve, consisting of a large sensory component (portio major; 170,000 fibers) and a smaller motor component (portio minor; 7,700 fibers). The sensory component is divided into three branches: the ophthalmic division (CN V1), the maxillary division (CN V2), and the mandibular division (CN

V3). [6] Differential diagnoses for TGN include herpes zoster (postherpetic neuralgia), dental disease, orbital disease, temporomandibular dysfunction, temporal arteritis, and post-traumatic neuralgias.[7] Idiopathic TGN often involves vascular compression of the trigeminal nerve, whereas symptomatic TGN can be caused by space-occupying lesions, multiple sclerosis, infections, and other factors.[8] Medically refractory idiopathic TGN is typically treated with a surgical procedure known as microvascular decompression (MVD).[9] Common vascular structures that may compress the TGN include the superior cerebellar artery (SCA), anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA), vertebral artery (VA), and posterior inferior cerebellar artery (PICA), as well as a persistent hypoglossal artery.[10] This study examines the improvement in pain, as measured by Visual Analog Scale (VAS) scores, before and after surgery, and conducts a cost-benefit analysis of the patients' medical expenses in the preoperative and postoperative periods.

Methods

This prospective study was conducted at the Tamil Nadu Government Multi-Super-Speciality Hospital, Omandurar Government Estate, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India, from January 2022 to February 2023, with a minimum follow-up period of six months. In the facial pain outpatient department, patients were evaluated using their medical history and imaging modalities to diagnose idiopathic trigeminal neuralgia (TGN). Cases of symptomatic trigeminal neuralgia, such as those caused by space-occupying lesions or multiple sclerosis (MS), and conditions mimicking TGN, including temporomandibular joint disorder, root canal pathology, migraine, cluster headache, post-herpetic neuralgia, trigeminal neuropathic pain, glossopharyngeal neuralgia, sphenopalatine neuralgia, geniculate neuralgia (Ramsay Hunt syndrome), and sinusitis, were ruled out with the aid of clinical diagnosis and imaging modalities.

After identifying TGN patients, the history of pain intensity was measured using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), and the frequency of paroxysmal events per month and involvement of the V1, V2, and V3 regions were recorded. Medical records were maintained to identify patients' responses to two-drug and three-drug regimens.[11] Patients with idiopathic TGN refractory to medical management or intolerant to neuropathic medication were selected for the study and motivated for surgery, while those who responded to medical management and were not motivated for surgery were excluded.

The preoperative severity of the disease was measured based on VAS scores, the number of paroxysmal events per month, Disease Adjusted

Loss of Life (DALY) per year, and the expenditure on medicine to control TGN paroxysmal attacks. Vascular loop involvement was identified using Magnetic Resonance Arteriogram (MRA). All patients underwent Microvascular Decompression (MVD) following standard textbook procedures. In the park-bench position, a lazy S incision was made, and a burr hole at the asterion site allowed for a retro-mastoid suboccipital craniotomy. Standard duratomy was performed, and all cerebellopontine angle cisterns were opened to control the drainage of cerebrospinal fluid. Vascular loop involvement was identified, and decompression between the vascular loop and the fifth cranial nerve was achieved using a Teflon patch.[12]

Postoperative outcomes were analysed from the first postoperative day using VAS pain scoring improvements. TGN neuropathic pain medications were withheld immediately postoperatively. Follow-up questionnaires assessed improvements in VAS scores, the reduction in the number of paroxysmal sequences per month, and the reduction in DALY numbers. The mean VAS score was 6.5, with the age range of female patients being 35 to 65 years and male patients 40 to 60 years. The mean number of paroxysmal episodes was two per month per patient, and the DALY ranged from twelve to fifteen days per year. Diagnosis was based on clinical history evaluations and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). Patients with idiopathic TGN refractory to medical management were selected for surgical management. All patients underwent retro-mastoid suboccipital craniotomy in the park-bench position with microscopic assistance. Duratomy was performed using an inverse 'K' manoeuvre, and cisterns were opened with microscopic assistance.

The cisterna magna, ponto-cerebellar cisterns, and mesencephalic cisterns were opened in a controlled manner. The upper third of the craniotomy site was concentrated to identify the fifth nerve neurovascular bundle. The superior cerebellar artery (SCA), vertebral artery (VA), basilar artery (BA), and anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA) were identified. Neurovascular decompression was performed with a Teflon patch. Orientation of the V1, V2, and V3 nerve roots with the fifth nerve nuclei was assessed, and any aberrant nerve routes were identified, and measures taken to rule out vascular compression. The average blood loss was 200 ml, and the average duration of the procedure was two hours.

Results

A total of 325 patients presented with facial pain symptoms at the outpatient department. Among them, 195 were female and 140 were male. The distribution of facial pain symptoms included 150

cases of migraine, 30 cases of temporomandibular joint pain, 80 cases of cluster headache, 30 cases of symptomatic trigeminal neuralgia (TGN), 15 cases of idiopathic TGN, and 30 cases of other conditions. Of the 15 idiopathic TGN patients, 10 were diagnosed with refractory TGN unresponsive to medical management and were selected for prospective studies and surgical management.

In this study group, the male-to-female ratio was 1:1. The mean age of female patients was 47.5 years, and the mean age of male patients was 51

years. The average TGN VAS score was 6.5, with patients experiencing an average of two paroxysmal episodes per month.

The Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) was 12 to 15 days per year. The average monthly cost of medication to manage paroxysmal episodes was INR 1200 to 1400 (USD 16-19) in the preoperative period, with patients experiencing an average of five paroxysmal episodes per month and a DALY index of 10 days per year.

Figure 1: Distribution of patients with facial pain symptoms

Intraoperative results involved a cerebellopontine angle approach using the park-bench position, a lazy 'S' incision, a retro mastoid suboccipital approach, and duratomy with cisternostomy and vascular loop identification. The average duration of surgery was two hours, with a mean blood loss of 200 ml. The vascular loop findings included the Superior Cerebellar Artery (SCA) in three out of ten patients, the Anterior Inferior Cerebellar Artery (AICA) in two patients, the Basilar Artery (BA) in one patient, the Vertebral Artery (VA) in two

patients, and the Persistent Hypoglossal Artery in one patient. Eight out of ten patients experienced a reduction in their VAS score to less than five immediately postoperatively. The average hospital stay was 10 days. The average number of neuropathic medications taken reduced from four to two in the first week postoperatively. Documented postoperative complications included transient pseudomeningocele in two patients and transient facial nerve palsy and eighth nerve palsy in one patient each.

Figure 2: Vascular loop findings

A cost-benefit analysis showed that the average preoperative monthly medication cost was INR 1200 (USD 12), while the average postoperative medication cost was INR 500 (USD 5.5).

Table 1: Distribution of postoperative complications

Complications	Number (Percent) N (%)
Infections	0 (0.0)
CSF leakage	0 (0.0)
Pseudomeningocele	2 (20.0)
Facial nerve palsy	1 (10.0)
8 th nerve damage	1 (10.0)

Discussion

Trigeminal neuralgia (TGN) is characterized by brief, intense, paroxysmal pain involving one or two branches of the fifth cranial nerve, often triggered by cutaneous stimuli.[13] Differential diagnoses for TGN include herpes zoster (postherpetic neuralgia), dental diseases, orbital diseases, temporomandibular joint dysfunction, temporal arteritis, root canal pathology, migraine, cluster headaches, trigeminal neuropathic pain, glossopharyngeal neuralgia, sphenopalatine neuralgia, geniculate neuralgia (Ramsay Hunt syndrome), sinusitis, and post-traumatic neuralgias.

TGN is classified into idiopathic and symptomatic forms. Idiopathic TGN is often caused by vascular compression from arteries such as the Superior Cerebellar Artery (SCA), Vertebral Artery (VA), Anterior Inferior Cerebellar Artery (AICA), and Posterior Cerebral Artery (PCA). Symptomatic TGN is attributed to space-occupying lesions, multiple sclerosis, and infections.

Surgical treatments for TGN include peripheral (postganglionic) procedures, percutaneous ganglion-level techniques, stereotactic radiotherapy, and microvascular decompression (MVD).[14-16] For idiopathic TGN unresponsive to medication, MVD is a common surgical intervention.[17] All percutaneous techniques aim to induce some degree of sensory loss, though they carry risks of neuropathic pain or dysesthesia in approximately 6% of cases and anaesthesia dolorosa in about 4%.[18] Other possible complications, though rare, include corneal numbness (4%), masseter weakness, other cranial nerve issues, and aseptic meningitis, with mortality being extremely low.[19]

Gamma Knife surgery (a form of stereotactic radiosurgery) provides pain relief comparable to percutaneous ganglion-level procedures, with remission rates of up to 69% at one year and 52% at three years according to several studies.[20] Postoperative outcomes such as VAS scores and DALY significantly improve after surgical management for idiopathic TGN. Transient complications from surgery can include cerebrospinal fluid leakage, pseudomeningocele, facial nerve palsy, and eighth nerve palsy. Studies

indicate favourable results from surgery, with remission rates of 85% at one year, 77% at three years, and 75% at five years based on multiple studies.[9, 21] After an 11-month follow-up in this institutional study, no further remissions were documented. Many medical centres have adopted MVD as their primary treatment approach, reporting generally better outcomes compared to less experienced centres.

Conclusion

This study underscores the efficacy of surgical interventions, particularly microvascular decompression (MVD), for managing idiopathic trigeminal neuralgia (TGN) that is refractory to medical treatment. With a significant reduction in pain scores and paroxysmal episodes post-surgery, MVD has demonstrated a favourable outcome in terms of patient quality of life and cost-effectiveness. The study also highlights the importance of precise differential diagnosis and the role of advanced imaging techniques in identifying vascular compression. Despite the risks of transient complications, the overall low incidence of severe adverse effects and the high rates of pain remission support the adoption of MVD as a primary treatment modality in experienced centres. Continued research and long-term follow-up are essential to further validate these findings and refine surgical techniques, ensuring optimal patient outcomes.

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